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Breast MRI in the prone position: impact on RF-induced heating of active implantable medical devices

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E-mail: yaoaiping@ncu.edu.cn**Keywords:** breast examination, prone, face-down, MRI, RF-induced heating, active implantable medical devicesSupplementary material for this article is available [online](#)

Abstract

Objective. Prone (face-down) postures, commonly used in breast examination, as well as in wrist and elbow imaging, change the the induced current path in the body and therefore the incident electric fields to the implants during MR examination, potentially leading to significant variations from risk predictions made in supine postures. The goal of this work is to investigate the impact of prone breast examination postures, compared to supine MR examination postures, on the RF-induced heating of medical implants. **Approach:** To assess these effects, the Virtual Population anatomical model Ella was modified with breast shapes typical of a prone examination, and posed with one or both arms raised above the head. The head was positioned either adjacent to the bore wall, typical for breast MR examinations, or centrally within the bore, similar to supine positioning. The RF-induced electric fields and worst-case power depositions were compared with those from the supine Ella model for representative generic pacemaker, deep brain stimulator (DBS), and cochlear implants, at breast imaging landmarks. **Main results.** The results indicate that prone positions typical of breast examination can lead to differences in incident electric field and corresponding RF-heating of, at least, up to 5 dB at 1.5 T, and up to 2.5 dB at 3.0 T, for cochlear implants, 1–2 dB for DBS, and 1 dB for pacemakers, compared to the corresponding supine imaging landmarks. **Significance.** These findings underscore the importance of considering patient posture in RF safety assessments of implantable medical devices in the head and neck regions. To avoid underestimation of local RF exposure near these implants, a comprehensive posture-aware safety protocol should be designed and considered during the RF safety evaluation and labeling.

1. Introduction

Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) has become an indispensable diagnostic tool across a wide range of clinical applications, including brain, cardiac, musculoskeletal, and breast imaging. However, MRI poses safety concerns for patients with active implantable medical devices (AIMDs) due to interactions between the radiofrequency (RF) fields and conductive implants, which may result in excessive heating and potential tissue damage (Bottomley and Andrew 1978, Bottomley and Edelstein 1981, Bottomley *et al* 1985, Nyenhuis *et al* 2005, Norris 2011). RF-induced heating remains one of the primary safety risks associated with MRI in patients with implants (Bhuva *et al* 2020), and its risk depends on the intensity and distribution of the induced *in vivo* electric fields in the patient (Yao *et al* 2021) as well as the geometry and positioning of the implant within the body (Navarro-Valverde *et al* 2022).

Ensuring patient safety during MRI scans of AIMD patients is a critical aspect of regulatory compliance. The ISO/IEC 10974 technical specification (ISO/IEC 2018) defines the procedures for MR safety evaluations of active medical implants during 1.5 T and 3.0 T cylindrical bore MR scans. It includes a 4-Tier approach for the evaluation of RF-induced heating and malfunctions with increasing complexity that reduces risk overestimation. Tier 1 and Tier 2 require the worst-case exposure field in the whole body (Tier 1) and at the implanted body region (Tier 2), and are not suitable for implants with elongated lead. Tier 3 is especially suitable for such elongated-lead implants. It decouples the RF interaction into two components: the implant's RF transfer function (Park et al 2007, ISO/IEC 2018), which characterizes how the implant responds to external electric fields, and the *in vivo* tangential incident electric field (E_{tan}), which represents the RF exposure within the human body. This separation significantly reduces the computational burden compared to Tier 4, which requires high-fidelity models of the human body, implant geometry, and MRI coil characteristics. Using the Tier 3 approach, the RF-induced power deposition near the implant's electrode can be estimated by integrating the transfer function with the incident electric field. This method allows for consideration of various clinical factors, such as patient anatomy (Murbach et al 2014), RF coil design (Lucano et al 2018), and imaging position (Yao et al 2019, Winter et al 2021, Wooldridge et al 2021), enabling more realistic and patient-specific safety assessments.

Despite significant advances in computational modeling and experimental validation techniques (Graf et al 2007, Mattei et al 2008, Murbach et al 2014, Sadeghi-Tarakameh et al 2022), most RF safety evaluations are based on human body models in a standard supine posture, which reflects the typical configuration for most MRI procedures, as well as the posture of the models used as data sources (volunteers or cadavers, typically supine). However, certain clinical imaging protocols require the patient to be positioned in a face-down or prone posture, particularly in breast MRI, as well as specific wrist and elbow scans. This alternative posture leads to variations in the induced E -fields in the patient. Further, in breast MRI, the patient is elevated with cushions and the hanging breasts are positioned close to the bore center, resulting in the patient head and shoulders being positioned closer to the RF coil than in supine postures, increasing capacitive coupling and further changing the incident field distribution. Despite its clinical relevance, the impact of prone MR examination postures on RF-induced heating has not been systematically investigated in the literature, possibly due to the lack of availability of prone anatomical datasets.

The objective of this study is to address this gap by evaluating the effects of prone breast MR examination postures on RF-induced heating for various common medical implant types. We employ computational simulations using high-resolution anatomical models to compare electric field distributions and Tier 3 power deposition across different implant scenarios. The findings of this study offer critical insights into posture-dependent RF heating risks and can inform more comprehensive safety evaluations for AIMD patients undergoing MRI in alternative imaging postures.

2. Method

2.1. Anatomical models and RF coil design

To numerically model both the standard and face-down MRI examination postures, the high-resolution anatomical model Ella from the virtual population (Gosselin 2014) was modified with breasts shaped typically of a prone patient during breast MRI, and posed and positioned in the following configurations, as illustrated in figure 1:

- **Ella (Supine)**: The standard Ella model in the supine position, centered within the bore.
- **Ella_Superman (Prone)**: The Ella model with prone breast tissues, posed with one arm raised above the head, and positioned with the hanging breast at the isocenter of the MRI bore.
- **Ella_Hands_Over (Prone)**: The Ella model with prone breast tissues, posed with both arms raised above the head, and positioned with the hanging breast at the isocenter of the MRI bore.
- **Ella_Superman_ISO (Prone)**: Same model as Ella_Superman, positioned with the torso at the isocenter of the bore, similar to supine Ella.
- **Ella_Hands_Over_ISO (Prone)**: Same model as Ella_Hands_Over, positioned with the torso at the isocenter of the bore, similar to supine Ella.

To evaluate RF exposure at both 1.5 T and 3.0 T MRI, high pass birdcage RF coils with a length of 60 cm, a diameter of 70 cm, and 16 rungs were designed and tuned to 64 MHz and 128 MHz, respectively. Each birdcage coil was excited at two ports (I and Q, located 90° apart) using orthogonal mode (equal amplitude with a fixed 90° phase shift), resulting in a circularly polarized B_1^+ field rotating clockwise when viewed along

the Z -axis (circular polarization). The coils were tuned to the fundamental (order-1) resonant mode, which is the only mode capable of generating a highly homogeneous B_1^+ field, as outlined in the IEC 60601-2-33 Standard (2010).

2.2. Implant routings

The difference between breast and supine posture on RF coupling was evaluated for generic but representative implants. These are isolated wires of different length with non-isolated tips in contact with the tissue, i.e. deep brain stimulators (DBS) (with length of 60 cm), PM (with length of 50 cm) and cochlear implant (with length of 10 cm). Twenty-four implant trajectories for generic DBSs, pacemakers (PM), and cochlear implants were modeled, each based on clinical input from a manufacturer of the respective implant type as shown in figure 2:

- **DBS_L (Left Side):** The lead was routed subcutaneously from the left pectoral region, along the side of the neck behind the ear, to the crown of the head, and terminated in the left thalamus.
- **DBS_R (Right Side):** Same as above, but mirrored to the right side of the body.
- **PM_L (Left Side):** The lead was routed from the left pectoral region through the veins to the left ventricle of the heart.
- **PM_R (Right Side):** Same as above, but on the right side.
- **EL (Extracochlear, Left):** Five unique extracochlear implant routings around the left ear (EL1, EL2, EL3, EL4, and EL5) as shown in figure 2 are used to represent typical clinical extracochlear lead positions.

Figure 2. Illustration of the implant routings considered: (a) right-side DBS (DBS_R) and five unique extracochlear (ER1, ER2, ER3, ER4, ER5); (b) left-side DBS (DBS_L) and five unique extracochlear (EL1, EL2, EL3, EL4, EL5); (c) five unique left-side intracochlear (IL1, IL2, IL3, IL4, IL5) and right-side intracochlear routings (IR1, IR2, IR3, IR4, IR5); and (d) left-side and right-side pacemaker (PM_L and PM_R).

- **ER (Extracochlear, Right):** Five representative extracochlear trajectories (ER1–ER5) were defined around the right ear.
- **IL (Intracochlear, Left):** Five intracochlear trajectories (IL1–IL5) were defined within the left cochlea.
- **IR (Intracochlear, Right):** Five intracochlear trajectories (IR1–IR5) were defined within the right cochlea.

2.3. Electromagnetic (EM) simulation setup

EM simulations were conducted using Sim4Life v8.0 (Zurich MedTech, ZMT AG, Switzerland) with a finite-difference time-domain solver. Each anatomical model was placed in its respective posture within the designed RF coils. The birdcage coils were tuned to the resonance frequency using broadband quadrature excitation through two ports on the same end ring, corresponding to an ideal circularly polarized current distribution, as shown in figure 1. Direct simulations were used for all shown results; in parallel, a subset of simulations were repeated using a Huygens' box approach based on the equivalence principle to model wave propagation by replacing a tuned empty birdcage RF coil (IT'IS 2019) with equivalent electric and magnetic surface currents on the closed surface of the simulation domain (Taflove and Hagness 2005), assuming the backscattering effect on the current distribution can be neglected. To verify this, the results of direct simulations and Huygens' box were compared and found to be within the numerical confidence interval of 0.2 dB (MDDT 2019) as shown in figures S3 and S4.

The computational domain was discretized using a maximum resolution of $2.0 \times 2.0 \times 2.0 \text{ mm}^3$. Tissue dielectric properties at 64 and 128 MHz were assigned according to the IT'IS Tissue Properties Database (Hasgall et al 2018).

The estimated confidence interval of the results is described in IT'IS (2019).

Figure 3. Comparison of mean $|E_{tan}|$ at Normal Operating Mode exposure of 1.5 T MRI (64 MHz) of supine Ella (black), modified Ellas for prone breast examination (red) and the prone Ella models shifted to isocenter (ISO) (blue). The maximum dB variation to the supine case is shown at the right for each lead.

2.4. Evaluation metrics

Three evaluation metrics were assessed and compared in this study:

- E_{tan} : The *in vivo* tangential root mean square electric field along the implant trajectory, used to compute Tier 3 power deposition in accordance with ISO 10974 (ISO/IEC 2018).
- mean $|E_{\text{tan}}|$: The average magnitude of the RMS tangential electric field amplitude along the implant path, which is proportional to the square of RF-heating if the phase distribution is similar.
- Specific absorption rate (SAR): Includes the whole-body averaged SAR (wbSAR) and head-averaged SAR as defined in IEC 60601-2-33 (2010), representing the average RF power absorption in the anatomical model. Additionally, the arm SAR, defined as the average SAR within the right arm of the anatomical models, was also evaluated.
- P_{dep} : The potential worst-case power deposition, defined as follows:

$$P_{\text{dep}} = A \cdot \left(\int_0^L h(l) \cdot E_{\text{tan}}(l) \cdot dl \right) \left(\int_0^L h(l) \cdot E_{\text{tan}}(l) \cdot dl \right)^* \quad (1)$$

where A ($W/(V/m)^2$) is a constant applied uniformly across all models, $E_{\text{tan}}(l)$ represents the incident tangential electric field along the implant trajectory for each clinical scenario, $h(l) = e^{j\phi}$ is the transfer function of the implant, where the amplitude of the transfer function is defined to be a constant of 1, and with phase ϕ being the conjugate phase of $E_{\text{tan}}(l)$ (considered as the potential worst-case phase condition, and L denotes the total length of the implant).

For each defined anatomical model and scenario, the above metrics were evaluated and compared under normal operating mode as defined in the IEC 60601-2-33 Standard (2010) (e.g. whole body SAR limits of 2.0 W kg^{-1} , head SAR limits of 3.2 W kg^{-1}).

3. Results

3.1. 64 MHz RF exposure

In general, for all implant routings, the prone Ella models exhibit similar E_{tan} field distributions compared to the supine Ella model, as shown in the supplementary material (figure S1). However, the magnitude of E_{tan} can vary significantly in the prone models. As illustrated in figure 3, changing the posture from the supine to the prone position, either with the Superman or Hands-Over configuration, results in an increase in the mean E_{tan} magnitude under Normal Operating Mode by approximately 2 dB for DBS, 1 dB for pacemakers, and nearly 5 dB for extracochlear and intracochlear implants. When the prone Ella models are shifted to isocenter (e.g. Ella_Hands_Over_ISO and Ella_Superman_ISO), the differences in E_{tan} magnitude are substantially reduced for cochlear and DBS routings, but not the pacemaker, indicating that the proximity of the head to the RF coil is significant. A similar trend is observed in the power deposition metric P_{dep} , as summarized in table 1 and table 2. As expected, the variations in E_{tan} translate to more than a 5 dB increase in power deposition for cochlear implants, and increases of 2 dB and 1 dB for DBS and pacemakers, respectively, when prone MRI postures are considered.

Figure 4 presents the mean E_{tan} magnitude of the supine Ella model as a function of imaging position under Normal Operating Mode. For pacemakers, Ella positioned at 200 mm (breast imaging landmark) exhibits the highest E_{tan} level. Thus, accounting for prone MR examination adds approximately 1 dB to the maximum E_{tan} level compared to standard supine imaging. Although the 200 mm imaging position does not yield the highest E_{tan} level for DBS and cochlear implants, incorporating the additional 2 dB and 5 dB margins observed in the prone positions increases their respective maximum E_{tan} levels by approximately 1 dB.

3.2. 128 MHz RF exposure

The E_{tan} distributions of implants under 3.0 T MRI are summarized in the supplementary material (figure S2). Similar to the 1.5 T MRI results, the prone Ella models show comparable E_{tan} field distributions to the supine model. However, as summarized in table 3, 4 and figure 5, the mean E_{tan} magnitudes vary across

Table 1. Mean E_{\tan} (V m^{-1}) amplitude of a generic implant along different implant routings inside the selected anatomical models at 1.5 T MRI (64 MHz).

Group	Implant	Ella	Prone breast exam		$ \Delta_1(\text{dB}) ^1$	Prone, isocenter		$ \Delta_2(\text{dB}) ^2$
			Superman	Hands_Over		Superman	Hands_Over	
DBS	DBS_L	105.5	128.4	120.2	1.7	114.2	109.1	0.7
	DBS_R	105.5	117.0	112.5	0.9	108.9	105.1	0.3
Pacemaker	PM_L	78.0	83.2	74.9	0.6	90.0	80.1	1.2
	PM_R	67.6	65.0	57.2	0.3	73.8	64.5	0.8
Extracochlear	EL1	68.0	94.6	89.7	2.9	69.2	70.9	0.4
	EL2	80.6	122.7	115.4	3.7	81.6	83.2	0.3
	EL3	75.9	118.6	112.3	3.9	77.5	79.0	0.3
	EL4	59.3	95.2	90.0	4.1	63.4	64.5	0.7
	EL5	87.4	139.4	131.6	4.1	87.4	89.4	0.2
	ER1	81.2	122.8	121.0	3.6	84.0	88.2	0.7
	ER2	70.2	115.4	113.9	4.3	75.4	79.0	1.0
	ER3	75.4	123.2	121.7	4.3	80.6	84.8	1.8
	ER4	59.8	104.0	103.2	4.8	70.7	73.8	1.0
	ER5	79.0	135.7	134.7	4.7	86.3	90.5	1.2
Intracochlear	IL1	58.1	83.6	77.4	3.2	64.9	63.0	1.0
	IL2	64.0	92.6	86.3	3.2	67.6	68.6	0.6
	IL3	51.0	75.9	71.2	3.5	56.2	56.7	0.9
	IL4	62.9	90.5	84.2	3.2	68.1	66.6	0.7
	IL5	56.2	84.2	78.0	3.5	64.5	62.4	1.2
	IR1	46.5	73.0	73.0	3.9	56.3	60.3	2.3
	IR2	53.9	93.1	93.6	4.0	68.1	73.3	1.8
	IR3	49.9	79.6	80.1	4.1	58.8	62.9	2.0
	IR4	49.9	78.5	79.0	4.0	59.3	64.0	2.2
	IR5	44.7	73.3	74.4	4.4	56.2	59.3	2.4

$|\Delta_1(\text{dB})|^1$: The maximum difference of $|E_{\tan}|$ between supine Ella and prone Ella at clinical breast exam position.

$|\Delta_2(\text{dB})|^1$: The maximum difference of the mean E_{\tan} value between Ella and maximum of the prone models with thorax at isocenter.

postures. At 3.0 T, the difference in mean E_{\tan} amplitude for pacemaker routings remains at approximately 1 dB, while the differences for DBS and cochlear implants are reduced to below 0.5 dB and 2.5 dB, respectively. Furthermore, unlike at 1.5 T, repositioning the prone Ella models to the iso-center plane does not significantly reduce these differences.

Similarly, the mean E_{\tan} magnitude of the supine Ella model as a function of imaging position under 3.0 T MRI is summarized in figure 6. For both DBS and pacemaker routings, the highest E_{\tan} levels are again observed at the 200 mm imaging position. Consequently, when accounting for face-down MRI postures in safety evaluations, an additional margin of 0.5 dB and 1 dB, respectively, should be considered. For cochlear implants, the posture-induced difference in E_{\tan} at 3.0 T is approximately 2.5 dB, resulting in a 1 dB higher maximum E_{\tan} level when the prone position is evaluated at the 200 mm imaging location.

Finally, the SAR values for both supine and prone Ella models are summarized in figure 7. In general, under equivalent B_1^+ exposure, whole-body SAR (wbSAR), head SAR, and arm SAR are higher at 3.0 T compared to 1.5 T MRI. Notably, for prone Ella models with raised arms, the arm SAR can exceed that of the supine models by more than twofold at 1.5 T and up to fourfold at 3.0 T MRI.

4. Discussion

This work investigates the potential impact of face-down MRI examinations on RF-induced *in vivo* electric fields and power deposition near implant electrodes. The major findings can be summarized as follows:

- (i) In general, changes in patient posture-including tissue deformation (e.g. hanging breast)-and positioning during face-down MRI examinations alter the induced field distribution, for the example, as shown in this paper resulting by more than 1 dB difference in the *in vivo* incident electric field and power deposition for DBS and pacemaker implants, and up to 5 dB for cochlear implants. This impact is obviously notably greater for cochlear implants, because changes in arm posture significantly affect

Table 2. P_{dep} (W) value of a generic implant along different implant routings inside the selected anatomical models at 1.5 T MRI (64 MHz).

Group	Implant	Ella	Prone (Non_ISO)		$ \Delta_1(dB) ^1$	Prone (ISO)		$ \Delta_2(dB) ^2$
			Superman	Hands_Over		Superman	Hands_Over	
DBS	DBS_L	4.00	5.92	5.19	1.7	4.70	4.30	0.7
	DBS_R	4.00	4.92	4.54	0.9	4.27	3.97	0.3
Pacemaker	PM_L	2.23	2.53	2.01	0.5	2.92	2.30	1.2
	PM_R	1.65	1.54	1.17	-0.3	1.97	1.49	0.8
Extracochlear	EL1	0.05	0.09	0.08	2.9	0.05	0.05	0.5
	EL2	0.06	0.15	0.13	3.7	0.07	0.07	0.3
	EL3	0.06	0.14	0.13	3.9	0.06	0.06	0.4
	EL4	0.04	0.09	0.08	4.0	0.04	0.04	0.9
	EL5	0.08	0.19	0.17	4.1	0.08	0.08	0.3
	ER1	0.06	0.15	0.15	3.7	0.07	0.08	0.8
	ER2	0.05	0.13	0.13	4.3	0.06	0.06	1.0
	ER3	0.06	0.15	0.15	4.3	0.07	0.07	0.9
	ER4	0.04	0.11	0.11	4.9	0.05	0.05	1.9
	ER5	0.06	0.18	0.18	4.7	0.07	0.08	1.1
Intracochlear	IL1	0.03	0.07	0.06	3.4	0.04	0.04	1.0
	IL2	0.04	0.09	0.07	3.3	0.05	0.05	0.5
	IL3	0.03	0.06	0.05	3.2	0.03	0.03	0.8
	IL4	0.04	0.08	0.07	3.0	0.05	0.04	0.5
	IL5	0.03	0.07	0.06	3.4	0.04	0.04	1.0
	IR1	0.02	0.05	0.05	3.9	0.03	0.04	2.1
	IR2	0.04	0.09	0.09	4.0	0.05	0.05	1.9
	IR3	0.02	0.06	0.06	4.3	0.04	0.04	2.2
	IR4	0.02	0.06	0.06	4.1	0.04	0.04	2.2
	IR5	0.02	0.05	0.05	4.6	0.03	0.04	2.7

$|\Delta_1(dB)|^1$: The maximum difference of the P_{dep} value between Ella and maximum of Prone model @ Non ISO.

$|\Delta_2(dB)|^1$: The maximum difference of the P_{dep} value between Ella and maximum of Prone model @ ISO.

the local field distribution near the ears. These enhancements are implant, location, and anatomically dependent and are not represented in the supine evaluation.

- (ii) Beyond posture effects, the influence of anatomical positioning with respect to the birdcage axis is more pronounced at 1.5 T (64 MHz). As observed in figures 3 and 7, both E_{\tan} levels and SAR metrics (wbSAR and head SAR) decrease by more than a factor of two when the prone models are moved from the edge to the iso-center plane at 1.5 T. The reduction is much less pronounced at 3.0 T (128 MHz), indicating weaker coupling effects at higher frequencies.
- (iii) For any implant potentially used during face-down MRI examinations, it is essential to include an appropriate analysis. It is recommended to perform a proper analysis of the risk of the specific implant as a function of the relevant postures or cover it within the uncertainty analysis, as it is not possible to reliably predict the potential worst-case anatomical scenario as shown in Kranold *et al* (2022). Radiologists may also consider an extra margin of safety when scanning prone patients if the labeling is unclear on this point.

Figure 5. Comparison of mean $|E_{tan}|$ at Normal Operating Mode exposure of 3.0 T MRI (128 MHz) of supine Ella (black), modified Ellas for prone breast examination (red) and the prone Ella models shifted to isocenter (ISO) (blue). The maximum dB variation to the supine case is shown at the right for each lead.

Finally, it is important to emphasize that the evaluation provided here assume accurate head SAR calculation by the MRI system, without erroneously including arm SAR in the head SAR assessment. If arm SAR is incorrectly treated as part of head SAR, the reported head SAR in prone Ella models could be substantially overestimated, by more than a factor of four at 3.0 T, as shown in figure 7. Such overestimation would lead to an artificial reduction in the E_{tan} level under the normal operating mode, as discussed in Goren et al (2024).

5. Conclusions

This study assessed whether the RF-induced heating risks for patients carrying active medical implants during prone (face-down) breast MR examination are covered by safety assessments performed with supine anatomical phantoms. By employing supine and prone variants of the high-resolution anatomical model Ella in various clinically relevant postures, we demonstrated that the deposited power at the electrode contacts can be increased by at least up to 1 dB higher for DBS and pacemakers, and to 5 dB for cochlear implants compared to the worst-case supine position. This is due to the different induced current distributions as a result of the postures. These findings underscore the importance of considering patient posture in RF safety assessments of implantable medical devices. To avoid underestimation of local RF exposure near these implants, a comprehensive posture-aware safety protocol should be designed and considered during the RF safety evaluation and labeling.

Table 3. Mean E_{tan} (V m^{-1}) amplitude of a generic implant along different implant routings inside the selected anatomical models at 3.0 T MRI (128 MHz).

Group	Implant	Ella	Prone (Non_ISO)			Prone (ISO)		
			Superman	Hands_Over	$ \Delta_1(\text{dB}) ^1$	Superman	Hands_Over	$ \Delta_2(\text{dB}) ^2$
DBS	DBS_L	109.9	111.1	92.6	0.1	118.2	109.6	0.6
	DBS_R	107.9	110.8	106.6	0.2	104.2	98.7	-0.3
Pacemaker	PM_L	76.9	76.0	66.8	-0.1	88.2	55.9	1.2
	PM_R	52.5	60.9	56.7	1.3	69.3	46.2	2.4
Extracochlear	EL1	76.8	85.9	66.5	1.0	78.1	63.0	0.2
	EL2	91.1	100.8	73.3	0.9	88.0	67.2	-0.3
	EL3	83.2	93.7	69.1	1.0	82.5	64.3	-0.1
	EL4	70.8	79.8	60.3	1.0	72.7	55.9	0.2
	EL5	98.9	110.7	79.2	1.0	93.9	70.6	-0.5
	ER1	102.1	117.6	103.6	1.2	91.2	80.4	-1.0
	ER2	90.3	107.3	94.5	1.5	81.1	70.8	-0.9
	ER3	96.0	114.0	100.2	1.5	86.7	75.8	-0.9
	ER4	73.3	97.9	86.7	2.5	75.8	66.2	0.3
ER5	98.3	124.5	108.8	2.1	92.4	79.8	-0.5	
Intracochlear	IL1	74.3	82.5	61.8	0.9	80.7	61.5	0.7
	IL2	81.5	87.6	63.8	0.6	84.2	63.4	0.3
	IL3	65.5	72.2	54.0	0.8	71.0	54.4	0.7
	IL4	81.3	90.5	64.1	0.6	85.7	64.9	0.5
	IL5	73.3	86.7	62.4	1.0	81.1	62.2	0.9
	IR1	60.0	78.0	70.0	2.3	61.7	55.1	0.3
	IR2	77.9	98.5	87.4	2.0	75.0	67.2	-0.3
	IR3	65.3	84.2	75.8	2.2	64.7	58.4	-0.1
	IR4	65.5	84.6	75.8	2.2	65.9	59.0	0.1
	IR5	58.2	77.1	69.3	2.4	61.1	54.8	0.4

$|\Delta_1(\text{dB})|^1$: The maximum difference of the mean $|E_{\text{tan}}|$ value between Ella and maximum of Prone model @ Non ISO.

$|\Delta_2(\text{dB})|^1$: The maximum difference of the mean $|E_{\text{tan}}|$ value between Ella and maximum of Prone model @ ISO.

Table 4. P_{dep} (W) value of a generic implant along different implant routings inside the selected anatomical models at 3.0 T MRI (128 MHz).

Group	Implant	Ella	Prone (Non_ISO)		$ \Delta_1(\text{dB}) ^1$	Prone (ISO)		$ \Delta_2(\text{dB}) ^2$
			Superman	Hands_Over		Superman	Hands_Over	
DBS	DBS_L	4.34	4.54	3.10	0.1	5.04	3.65	0.6
	DBS_R	4.19	4.42	4.09	0.2	3.90	3.51	-0.3
Pacemaker	PM_L	2.13	2.08	1.60	-0.1	2.83	1.12	1.2
	PM_R	1.01	1.35	1.21	1.3	1.78	0.77	2.4
Extracochlear	EL1	0.06	0.07	0.04	1.0	0.06	0.04	0.2
	EL2	0.08	0.10	0.05	0.9	0.08	0.04	-0.3
	EL3	0.07	0.09	0.05	1.0	0.07	0.04	-0.1
	EL4	0.05	0.06	0.04	1.0	0.05	0.03	0.2
	EL5	0.10	0.07	0.06	-1.3	0.09	0.05	-0.5
	ER1	0.10	0.14	0.11	1.2	0.08	0.06	-1.0
	ER2	0.08	0.12	0.09	1.5	0.07	0.05	-0.9
	ER3	0.09	0.13	0.10	1.5	0.08	0.06	-0.9
	ER4	0.05	0.10	0.07	2.5	0.06	0.04	0.3
ER5	0.10	0.15	0.12	2.1	0.09	0.06	-0.6	
Intracochlear	IL1	0.06	0.07	0.04	0.9	0.06	0.04	0.7
	IL2	0.07	0.08	0.04	0.6	0.07	0.04	0.3
	IL3	0.04	0.05	0.03	0.9	0.05	0.03	0.7
	IL4	0.07	0.07	0.04	0.6	0.07	0.04	0.5
	IL5	0.05	0.07	0.04	1.0	0.07	0.04	0.9
	IR1	0.04	0.06	0.05	2.3	0.04	0.03	0.3
	IR2	0.06	0.10	0.08	2.0	0.06	0.04	-0.4
	IR3	0.04	0.07	0.06	2.2	0.04	0.03	-0.1
	IR4	0.04	0.07	0.06	2.2	0.04	0.03	0.1
IR5	0.03	0.06	0.05	2.4	0.04	0.03	0.4	

$|\Delta_1(\text{dB})|^1$: The maximum difference of the P_{dep} value between Ella and maximum of Prone model @ Non ISO.

$|\Delta_2(\text{dB})|^1$: The maximum difference of the P_{dep} value between Ella and maximum of Prone model @ ISO.

Data availability statement

All data that support the findings of this study are included within the article (and any supplementary information files).

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